

Transaction Analysis on Ethereum Network Using Machine Learning: A Proposed System

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Abstract:- Ethereum, a well-known blockchain's most famous implementation builds and deploys a decentralized application where users can transact with cryptocurrency using smart contracts. The latest technological developments in cryptocurrencies and the benefits associated with them have been hidden by a number of illegal activities on the network. Like bribery, phishing scam, money laundering and fraud etc. The 'Pseudo-anonymous' nature of the participants in Ethereum blockchain network leads to cause difficulty in detecting illicit behavior of the users. Anomalies must be detected and resolved quickly to ensure participant trust in the largest blockchain platforms. There is a lot of work on detailed analysis of Ethereum transactions in terms of how well they work, but this research is the first to the best of my knowledge to detect anomalies in Ethereum transaction records. To achieve our goal, we have extracted more comprehensive feature of Ethereum transaction data to get rid of the shortcomings of existing work. We have used SMOTE technique to deal with highly imbalanced dataset and implemented five supervised-machine-learning model, Logistic-Regression, KNN, Decision-tree, Random-Forest and SVC classifier to access and compare the best performer among them. Random Forest Outperforms with accuracy of 98%. We evaluated the accuracy, precision, and F-value of each method and backed them up with experimental results.

Keywords:- Blockchain, Ethereum, Cryptocurrency, Smart Contracts, Anomaly Detection.

I. INTRODUCTION

Blockchain is a growing collection of blocks of digital records of currency transactions, conceived by Satoshi Nakamoto [1] to create a decentralized payment system. Recently, blockchain are in trend in computer technology, and blockchain technology as a whole will lead to major changes in economy of nation [2]. Cryptocurrencies or digital assets are the most vital and famous blockchain applications in terms of economy. The Bitcoin project is the latest successful huge implementation for the block-chain technology. Ethereum is considered to be the second largest blockchain application supporting smart-contracts, cryptocurrency (Ether), are the second huge crypto-currency [3]. While, due to rapid growth of

Ethereum, breeding ground for various cybercrimes due to its advantages of anonymity and low transfer costs, as well as its huge economic value has been increased [4]. An initial-coin-offering (ICO) provides funding technique for block-chain applications where investors receive tokens in exchange of their monetary investment. However, it is currently reported that more than 10% of ICOs issued on Ethereum are victims of various types of fraud, including phishing scams; Ponzi based crimes, etc. [5]. Detailed report by analysis, source investigative & safety management software for digital cash or virtual-currencies, in 2021, crypto-based crime hit a new high with \$14 billion in illegal addresses during the year, which is over \$7.8 billion. In 2020 [6], this indicates that financial security needs to be assured as it become an important concern to get over block-chain environment. However, between the many risk concerns associated with block-chain-based digital cryptocurrencies; Fraudulent transactions attributed for over 50% of all Ethereum cybercrimes in 2017, and this type of fraud poses a major security threat to Ethereum trading [7]-[8]. When using Ethereum transaction records to detect fraudster we may encounter following problems which may cause difficulties in the detection of fraud.

While dealing with real time Ethereum transaction data detection of malicious users is very difficult, as they are very few in such a huge transaction records, finding defaulter are like searching a needle in a haystack. We are experiencing the same problem due to excessive data imbalance nature of the dataset.

The diversity of the Ethereum trading system reflects the diversity of addresses, such as wallets, stock exchanges, and well-known ICOs [9], but the trading of typical loss accounts is relatively small. Using up-to-date information to distinguish between malicious and non-malicious email addresses can be very difficult in many networks.

The Ethereum fraud detection concept is a classification concept in machine learning. The success of this process is related to the policy chosen and the accessibility of the information provided. Feature extraction that accurately differentiates between malicious and non-malicious transactions can be effectively used for classification models [10]-[11]. The main contribution of this article is we can detect the malicious nodes in the Ethereum network with a comparatively high probability. The Proposed method does not

classify the genuine user as malicious. Many tests conducted on the Ethereum trading network confirmed success of the dedicated method for detecting fraudulent transactions.

II. RELATED-WORK

The concept of block-chain was introduced to store information in registers of records that are distributed over decentralized networks that are part of the blockchain infrastructure. The Bitcoin infrastructure has attracted many applications, and the open and close nature of the blockchain technology is overall used in crypto currencies. Ethereum is opensource place.

The idea of Ethereum was first introduced at the end of 2013, growth of Ethereum program start in initially 2014. But with rapid growth of blockchain it becomes popular. Scams on digital currency used as name exchanges and new technologies are not uncommon. Anomaly detection for the Ethereum network and other public channel currencies has been extensively and comprehensively reviewed existing literature, several detection methods suggested. In 2016, Pham et al. [13]- [15] Extracted bitcoin properties, read them using power law and density law from custom graph and transaction graph network approaches, and found three non-uniform values of 1 in 30 known bitcoins using Local-Outlier-Factor One-Class-Support-Vector-Machine and Mahala-Nobis-Distance models. Vasek and Moore [16] conducted preliminary research Bit-coin scammers, identified 4 types of fraud: 1) Ponzi-schemes; 2) Mining; 3) fake wallets; 4) Fraud Many smart contracts and ICO security studies [17] - [20]] have been analyzed on the Ethereum platform. For example, Atzei et al. [17] studied the risk of Ethereum smart-contracts and discussed key attacks and vulnerabilities. A series of fraud detection studies on the Ethereum platform were conducted to study smart contracts and the first complete overview of the Ethereum Ponzi scheme. Later, Chen et al. [21] proposed a method to investigate complex Ponzi-schemes using data-mining and machine-learning techniques. In 2017, Toyoda et al. [22] Analysis of Bitcoin transaction patterns related to High Product Investment Plan (HPIP) affiliates. Using large-scale supervised learning to extract known transaction patterns and features of tokenized Bitcoin addresses, they identified fifteen hundreds and more bit-coin index with a bounce rate of 83% and false-positive rate of 4.4%. In 2018, Vasek et al. [23] Ponzi-based survival-analysis methods that identify factors influencing Bitcoin fraud. He accumulated 1,424 posts on Bitcointalk to come up with 1780 different Bitcoin Ponzi schemes and found a positive correlation between the numbers. The interactions between scammers and their victims determine the duration through survival analysis. The existence of the transaction report provides a great source of computer technology that can help detect fraud in Ethereum mining transactions [24]. Although most fraudsters have traditionally relied on phishing-emails and webpages to find important data from consumers, modern fraud techniques eyes on how to find mails or webpages that contain them. There may be false information [25] - [26].

III. METHODOLOGY

Here, we first describe the overview of the dataset used and then describe all the features extracted from the Ethereum transaction record dataset. The Section is concluded with the description of machine learning classifiers proposed for this study.

A. Data Description

In this study we obtain the Ethereum transaction data from Infura API. They provided secure and reliable accessibility to Ethereum API and IPFS gateways [28]. We will label the transactions with instances of legitimate and malicious with 0 and 1 respectively.

B. Feature Extraction

Based on the measured variables provided by the Ethereum network, we are trying to introduce more meaningful features that will help our learning algorithm achieve its desired goals. In total, 16 features were extracted from the Ethereum transaction network.

- Currency features: max val received, Avg val received, avg val sent, total ether sent, total ether balance
- Network features: Average minimum between sent transition, Average minimum between found transition, Difference in between first and last minutes time, Sent transition, found transition, Number of Created-Contracts
- ERC20 features: ERC20 total Ethereum found, ERC20 total Ethereum sent, ERC20 total Ether sent contract, ERC20 unique sent address, ERC20 unique recent token name

C. Pre-Processing

Data Preprocessing is a crucial step while using machine learning classifiers as it contains noise and redundancy. Work is needed to clean up data and reduce / eliminate noise and to adapt to a machine learning model to improve its accuracy and efficiency.

D. Proposed Method

The objects in the dataset obtained by Infura API were Unlabeled as discussed in Section 3.1, hence in this study, the appropriate algorithm will be selected to detect the odd value by accumulating the basic structure of the clusters present in the network. The compared algorithms are Decision Tree Classifier, Logistic Regression, KNN, Random Forest, and SVC. The results obtained using these methods will be discussed with an indication of their accuracy in the "Results" section.

IV. RESULT

In this section, we will discuss the experimental results of the selected supervised machine learning classifiers and present the comparative study with the help of fig. 7.

❖ *Performance-Evaluation-Metrics*

To find the execution of many techniques in terms of anomaly find problem, we accept 3 analysis metrics, namely, precision, recall, and F-score as the main evaluation metrics.

The three metrics are defined as follows:

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{True Positive}}{\text{True-Positive+False-Positive}}$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{True Positive}}{\text{True-Positive+False-Negative}}$$

$$\text{F-score} = 2 \times \frac{\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}$$

A. *Classification-Performance*

In this Section, we first present the classification report of each method followed by their confusion matrix, which gives the accuracy measures of each classifier. Next we will provide a comparison report of accuracy and f-score of selected methods applied for classification.

Table 1. Classification-Report-of-Logistic-Regression

	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-score(%)	Support
0	97	88	92	1547
1	68	88	77	422
Accuracy	-	-	83	1969
Macro Avg	82	88	85	1969
Weighted Avg	90	88	89	1969

Fig.1. Confusion Matrix of Logistic Regression

Table 2: Classification Report of Decision Tree

	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-score (%)	Support
0	97	88	92	1547
1	68	88	77	422
Accuracy	-	-	96	1969
Macro Avg	82	88	85	1969
Weighted Avg	90	88	89	1969

Fig.2. Confusion Matrix of Decision Tree Classifier

Table 3. Classification Report of Random Forest

	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
0	0.99	0.98	0.98	1547
1	0.93	0.95	0.94	422
Accuracy	-	-	0.98	1969
Macro Avg	0.96	0.97	0.96	1969
Weighted Avg	0.97	0.97	0.89	1969

Fig.3. Confusion Matrix of Random Forest

Table 4: Classification Report of SVC

	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
0	0.99	0.98	0.98	1547
1	0.93	0.95	0.94	422
Accuracy	-	-	0.84	1969
Macro Avg	0.96	0.97	0.96	1969
Weighted Avg	0.97	0.97	0.89	1969

Table 5: Classification Report of KNN

	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
0	0.99	0.98	0.98	1547
1	0.93	0.95	0.94	422
Accuracy	-	-	0.84	1969
Macro Avg	0.96	0.97	0.96	1969
Weighted Avg	0.97	0.97	0.89	1969

Fig.4. Confusion Matrix of Support Vector Classifier

Fig.5. Confusion Matrix of KNN

Fig 7. Performance Comparison of selected machine learning classifiers

Considering the nature of dataset, first we have chosen Logistic Regression model which gives accuracy of 83% shown in table 1. It correctly identifies 373 fraud cases out of 422 that are quite impressive which get improves in SVC with 84% accuracy when model is evaluated on the test set. The test set contains 422 malicious and 1547 non-malicious data points. SVC gives better results than KNN when tested on similar data points. We get 96% accuracy while using Decision tree classifier where we trained the model on ground truth. Figure 2 shows that decision tree correctly classified 392 out of 422 fraud cases. The results of Random Forest shows that it is doing slightly better than Decision tree when it comes to non-fraud transaction, flagged 29 cases as fraud when they were actually non-fraud. When it comes to identify fraud cases RF fails to detect 21 fraud cases out of 422 shown in fig 3, suggesting the best recall score. Considering the overall performance Random Forest is the choice that we want. In this study we are not. In this paper we care more about the transactions that are actually fraud rather than which were treated as non-fraud.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

To fulfil the objective of this paper, we have systematically investigated the detection of fraudulent transactions in Ethereum via machine learning classifiers. Specifically, Proposed a SMOTE method to deal with highly imbalanced data sets using features extracted from Ethereum transaction history using machine learning algorithms. The study in this article is an improvement on similar reports in terms of the number of known cases of fraud. Based on the efficiency of our proposed discovery system and the characteristics of the Ethereum business network, the performance of real Ethereum business records demonstrates that Random Forests outperform other properties. From this paper, we can conclude that the principle is implemented in Ethereum trading using machine learning methods. The machine can determine the level of suspicion by classifying each address as malicious or non-malicious by tracking of Potential Data Points.

The main challenge in this paper that instances are unlabeled and therefore become tough to validate results. The issue of malicious transactions detected in Ethereum has not been effectively investigated because it provides security risks to users of Ethereum. As a work of research in this area, we want to attract more interest and work in this area. With more domain knowledge and more accurate analysis, more systematic and general algorithm can be dedicate for Ethereum, other transaction wallets. In Future Parallel segmentation method [24] can be applied to detect windings.

In this way we find the proper structure of a fixed graph to identify anomalies.

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